

PREDICTING THE TOTAL STRUCTURAL INTENSITY IN BEAM STRUCTURES USING THE SPECTRAL ELEMENT METHOD

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1. INTRODUCTION

One of the most commonly used numerical methods in vibration analysis is the Finite Element Method (FEM). Although the FEM-based approach is normally adequate to solve vibration problems, the computational cost and data storage demands can become prohibitive when performing medium and high frequency analysis of large structures.

One of the alternative techniques used to analyze the dynamical behavior of structures is Structural Intensity (SI). Using SI, power flow paths through a physical model under investigation can be predicted, and dominant flow paths can be identified. Structural vibration and noise control strategies can then be sought using the dominant flow path information. The use of SI techniques in this kind of problem may be very useful as SI combines both force and velocity in one concept.

In this paper, the formulations for SI calculations are briefly reviewed. A “z-shaped” beam structure, which has the three types of vibrating waves: longitudinal, flexural and torsional is investigated.

The SI computations are based on predicted vibration responses. These responses are calculated using the Spectral Element Method (SEM). The SEM, introduced by Doyle [1], is formulated directly in the frequency domain and thus present many advantages in handling vibration problems efficiently even at high frequencies. Perhaps the most important and unique advantage of this method is that it incorporates the use of the so-called throw-off elements, which are conduits for energy propagation out of the system.

The example beam is plunged into a sand box to simulate an anechoic termination. This termination is modeled via SEM by the throw-off element and localized stiffness elements. The numerically predicted results are then qualitatively compared with the experimentally predicted results.

1. STRUCTURAL INTENSITY FORMULATIONS

SI can be defined as active power per unit area, and can then be written as the instantaneous applied force times the instantaneous resulting velocity at a given point. The average SI, $\langle P \rangle_t$, is computed as the time-averaged product of this force and the component of velocity in the direction of the force. In spectral analysis, the propagating quantity of power can be written as,

$$\langle P \rangle_t = \frac{1}{2} \Re \{ F(\omega) \dot{v}^*(\omega) \} \quad (1)$$

where * denotes the complex conjugate and $F(\omega)$ and $\dot{v}(\omega)$ are the complex amplitudes of the force and the velocity, respectively.

The SI analysis developed here considers a single beam member that exhibits three main wave types: axial, bending, and torsional. The analysis of these three types will be done separately. The formulations for these analyses can be found in Ahmida & Arruda [2]. For the case of three-dimensional beam elements, three orthogonal directions are considered. The total time-averaged SI at any arbitrary point in the 3-D frame element is given as the sum of the components in all directions.

2. SPECTRAL ELEMENTS

Two different types of beam elements can be used: 2-noded and throw-off. Three different spectral elements (which can be combined in a single 12-DOF element) are used for the three possible deformations: bar, beam and shaft elements. Spectral analysis represents the solutions in the form

$$u(x, t) = \sum \hat{u} e^{-i(kx - \omega t)} \quad (2)$$

where k is the wave number. The formulations for the stiffness matrices for the different elements can be reviewed in Doyle [2].

3. NUMERICAL MODELING AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In order to investigate the aforementioned SEM formulations for SI analysis, a non-planar z-shaped beam structure was used. The beam is plunged at one end into a sandbox, to simulate an anechoic termination, and is excited by a shaker at the other end. A diagram of the experimental configuration is shown in Figure 1.

The warped z-shaped aluminum beam (cross section 25mm x 3.4mm) used consists of one straight beam folded three times making four spans (ab, bc, cd, de). Span ab is parallel to the plane xz, with 700 mm plunged in the sandbox. Span bc makes 39° with the plane xz. Span cd makes 12° with the plane xy, 12° with the plane xz and is twisted 35° with respect to its neutral axis. Span de makes 45° with span cd. The latter is excited at its free end. This kind of configuration generates longitudinal, transversal and torsional vibration components at the measurement zone. The beam structure is modeled with SEM by using just five spectral elements: four are 2-noded and one is throw-off

Figure 1. Physical model.

to simulate the anechoic termination. A frequency range of 0-400 Hz is analyzed with 0.5 Hz resolution.

The comparison between numerical and experimental results in Figures 2-4 is only qualitative, as we have not tried to characterize exactly the impedance of the sand-box termination in the SEM model.

Figure 2. Experimental structural intensity and structural intensity components

4. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The SEM was used to model structural intensity in 3-D frame structures and produced very promising results vis-à-vis the comparison between the input power and the SI as a validation tool for the method.

When comparing the predicted with the experimental results, the differences are mainly due to the fact that the sand box is not anechoic, and reflects part of the incoming energy back to the beam, while the throw-off element dissipates all the incoming energy.

Figure 3. SEM structural intensity results without localized stiffness elements

Figure 4. SEM structural intensity results with localized stiffness elements

For a better agreement between the SEM results and the experimental results, the use of localized stiffness elements in the SEM model was necessary to simulate the reverberation, and showed more satisfactory results. The values of these localized stiffness elements are critical and should be chosen such that they reproduce the actual impedance of the sand box. The use of experimentally derived impedance should produce more accurate predictions.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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6. REFERENCES

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